

PRINCIPLES FOR THE CREATION OF ARTIFICIAL GENERAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: As advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) gain speed and artificial general intelligence (AGI) becomes a goal in the global race towards technical dominance, this paper presents much needed foundational principles to govern the creation and operation of autonomous AGI systems. The principles are placed in context with OECD's AI principles as a result of their incorporation of input from major AI expertise and their consequent global influence. Within this context, our principles originate from an engineering and scientific perspective to enhance and improve upon OECD's AI principles as well as introduce concepts novel to OECD for AGI creation and governance. The principles also target foreseeable issues of advancing AI technology and therefore complement current emerging regulatory frameworks. For these reasons, it is our view that the principles we propose are to be adopted and ratified through international cooperation across salient institutions that influence the governance and creation of AI systems.

Keywords: Artificial General Intelligence, Human-Centered Design, Governance, Transparency, Accountability

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence Principles: Context and recent history

As artificial intelligence (AI) evolves from highly focused or weak AI towards more broad or strong AI, there continues to be a rise in interest to achieving and adopting evermore advanced forms of AI systems, including artificial general intelligence systems (AGI); systems that can execute diverse real-world tasks in a manner comparable to human intelligence in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, and functionality, and with progressively increasing levels of autonomy [1] to [16]. In realizing the merits of adopting AI technology, major countries have established, or are currently working to set, guidelines, regulations and principles to encourage the progress of AI and enable policymakers to address risks stemming from its adoption [17], [18], [20], [21], [22]. To this regard, the United States (US) National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) drafted an AI risk management framework in July 2024 to help organizations identify risks posed by generative AI and propose appropriate risk management actions [22]. Further, the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) released a set of principles for responsible design and use of AI technology in October 2022 [18]. Further, on 13th March 2024, the European Union (EU) adopted principles aiming to establish safeguards on general-purpose AI and to foster innovation and recently published them in the Official Journal of the EU AI Act [17], [23]. The United Kingdom (UK) established the AI Safety Institute in November 2023 to enable safe and reliable development and deployment of advanced AI systems [20], and in 2021 and 2022 China introduced binding regulations on AI applications towards governance of AI technology [24]. Furthermore, the high urgency on the governance and development of AI technology and frameworks towards safe and responsible use continues to be an area of active research [19]. Such attention to establishing principles of AI highlights the increased significance of governing AI systems

The purpose of this paper in context

In this paper, we propose principles to govern the creation and operation of autonomous AGI systems; systems we term as AI beings or AI agents. The principles we propose have been developed independently from a policy standpoint. Specifically, we reason that the perspective we take towards establishing the principles stems from the engineering, construction and operation of AI beings as opposed to a predominantly legal or regulatory viewpoint, thereby integrating the consideration of the principles into the foundational design of said systems. The principles we propose also include a focus on broad implications and issues we perceive to be faced in the future for AI, as well as issues associated with its current adoption. We specifically place our proposed principles in context with the AI principles from the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), in recognition of their global influence, adopted by the G20 in June 2019 [21], [25]. We believe that the principles we propose can enhance the OECD AI principles by a) widening the scope of application of OECD's AI principles and b) introducing ideas, novel to OECD's AI principles, to facilitate governing the creation and operation of AGI. Moreover, the principles we propose also expand upon the current OECD principles' focus on AI, heading *towards AGI*, thereby broadening the impact of principle adoption. We also reason that targeting of foreseeable issues of AI technology with these principles complements current regulatory frameworks, which focus on current and near future frontier AI model issues facing AI technology. Therefore, we advocate that our principles should be universally accepted as the minimum standards for creating and governing AI beings. It is our view that policymakers ought to initially adhere to principles (such as the principles in this paper) at a broad high-level before gradually moving towards a more strict and narrowly defined rule-based definition. Such a view is supported in recently adopted AI governance frameworks [26]. Various stakeholders, including AI creators, governments, international organizations, and other influential institutions, should collaborate to ratify and enhance relevant laws, regulations, and standards based on these principles to towards responsible use of AGI.

Through the proposal of these principles, we also aim to shine light and stimulate further debate on questions we foresee to arise before, during, and after the creation and operation of AI beings. These questions include topics such as the definition of intelligence, the form of the beings demonstrating increasing levels of higher intelligence, their capability to perceive environments through multiple sensory systems, their capability to comprehend and articulate thoughts through language understanding. The questions can also allude to AI beings' ability to recognize or act on emotion, and potentially demonstrate a form of awareness, in addition to bias and ethics considerations.

The structure of this paper

To establish an organization of concepts for the principles we propose, this paper is structured into two themes. The first theme is the purpose of creating AI beings. Starting from defining an intent behind creating AI beings, we reason that one way to best realize the value from creating AI beings is to view them as agents that can achieve two purposes: a) serve as tools that best serve humans, and b) possess the independence to act with progressively less supervision. As such, our view is to target a hybrid objective from the creation of AI beings: The purpose of creating AI beings is to serve as semi-independent tools that serve human interests. Four principles are

proposed in this first theme. The second theme surrounds the topic of interaction. Specifically, a) the interplay between humans and AI beings, b) the communication amongst AI beings, and c) the assimilation of humans and AI beings. In this theme, eight principles are proposed. This paper is structured in a way that first states the principle, and then presents the discussion specific to that principle. The discussion includes an identification of the discipline underlying the conception of the principle. Such a discussion is crucial for connecting the discipline to the intended impact from the principle. Disciplines discussed include computer science, cognitive science, engineering, and ethics.

Worthy of note is that our thought process that drives the production of the presented principles is based on an approach that prioritizes the well-governed creation and operation of AI beings in the service of humans; a human-centered approach that places humans at the focal point of the existence of AI beings. We adopt the following definition of a human-centered approach [27]: an approach “with a primary focus on human experiences, needs, and overall well-being.” This approach is intended to prioritize human rights and consider societal implications such as the effects on well-being, culpability, and potential consequences from the introduction and use of AI beings.

Section 1: The purpose of creating AI beings

This theme addresses the intended purpose for creating AI beings. As stated earlier, we hold the view that the purpose of creating AI beings is to function as semi-independent tools that serve humans. As a result, the following four principles emerge.

Section 1.1: Principle #1

Principle #1:

An AI being that cannot explain the cause of its actions and the driving factors of its decision-making process is an AI being that should not be released into society to serve humans.

The challenge of creating an intelligent AI being is broad with many implications relating to its functioning. Such a consideration applies if AI beings were conceived as tools designed to serve humans, or beings that function in their own right (with some independence), when acting alongside humans. We believe that the continued existence, and thus development, of intelligent AI beings necessitates the continued *ability of the AI beings' human creators to understand the reasons underlying the decisions or actions that the AI beings take when acting alongside humans.* We reason that such an ability is vital towards realizing sustainable, well-governed, and safe service from AI beings in present and future human societies. We believe that such an ability is crucial for the following two reasons.

Section 1.1.1: A practical approach to continuously improve the performance of AI beings

One reason for pursuing the ability to identify the reasons for an AI being's decisions and actions stems from the initiative to continuously improve the performance of the AI beings as they carry out their intended functions. A designer of AI beings (whose purpose includes functioning as a tool to best serve humans) ought to be able to identify components of the AI being's design, or code, that need improvement towards enhanced efficiency and accuracy. One practical way to identify such areas of improvement (or areas where errors exist) is to *interrogate* the AI beings in a way that enables their developers to establish the underlying reasoning behind the AI beings' actions and decisions. Such an approach may alleviate the need for costly, highly detailed, and exhaustive data and code inspections for each AI being, which can become untenable as the quantity of data increases and the sophistication of AI beings approaches that of humans. Furthermore, research [28] indicates that enabling the AI beings to articulate their reasoning enables reviewing the AI being's logic to determine if the logic suffers from biases, prejudices, or flaws that require taking corrective measures before the AI being may carry out an action. One point to highlight is that this principle is primarily concerned with the ability of the AI being or agent, upon being questioned, to describe the underlying factors *within its knowledge set* that drove its decision. Indeed, an event in which the AI being does not adequately, or completely fails to, respond to such questioning is deemed an event that defines an area where the AI being's logic may be flawed or in need of improvement as the event highlights a risk from the continued deployment of the AI being. Risk management directives to be taken when such events occur include quarantining the AI being to facilitate tending to its enhancement without any unanticipated downstream effects.

Section 1.1.2: Assisting in demystifying AI beings

As AI beings become more advanced, their design, construction, dataset and coding parameters will gradually lose transparency, making their behavior and design opaque. Such loss of transparency leads to a concern that the AI beings' reasoning process may become misaligned with, or obscure to, humans [29]. One way to mitigate such a risk is to interrogate the AI beings to determine the transparency of their reasoning and its alignment to that of humans. Furthermore, we reason that assessing the ability of an AI being to *articulate the priority or importance* it attaches to its reasons in a way that mimics human communication fits closely with recent efforts to understand the role of language and its use towards understanding communication between humans and AI beings based on perceived contextual cues [30] to [33]. Indeed, research [34] refers to the argument that interaction with an AI system at an arbitrarily deep level can shed great insight into the processes it uses to generate its output. Therefore, embedding a principle that requires AI beings to have the ability to explain their reasoning process, ought to greatly demystify their operation once they reach a level of complexity that enables them to operate with some autonomy alongside humans.

The reasoning adopted in sections 1.1.1 and 1.1.2 stems from considerations in computer science and engineering, along with the perspective from the cognitive aspect of understanding the role of language in communication between humans and AI. This reasoning provides a context and an engineering foundation to principle 1.3

from the OECD AI principles, named “Transparency and explainability”. Indeed, our principle enables the *AI actors* (defined as those who play an active role in the AI system lifecycle, including organizations and individuals that deploy and/or operate AI) to create AI beings with the requirement that the AI being is able to provide information to identify the reasoning that leads it to take an action, as well as the requirement for fostering an understanding of AI systems that includes their capabilities and limitations.

Section 1.2: Principle #2

Principle #2:

Given human-centered approach espoused here, the human form is very likely to serve as the most efficient blueprint for creating AI beings. As such, it is not only permissible, but currently desirable to base AI beings’ form (i.e., internal reasoning and physical embodiment) on the human form.

The creation of AI beings requires that they have the ability to perceive their environments in ways that best enable them to respond to multisensory information and environmental changes that require their action. Furthermore, the AI beings’ design ought to include amongst its priorities, the efficiency in a) conception of a response and decision-making on the most relevant action and b) executing the selected action.

The multiplicity of the architectures of reasoning structures (e.g., solid structures with rigidly defined connections between interacting components vs. liquid structures with more variable connections) has been researched in studies [35] focused on foundations of cognition. The findings hint that liquid structures potentially play more of a role in advanced AI reasoning structures. Such a finding suggests the importance of considering the idea that novel kinds of thinking structures may be more suited for specific tasks and environments. As a result, one type of structure for devising or designing AI beings’ reasoning and acting capabilities should not be favored over another structure. Yet, other studies [31], [36] also hint at the relatively more enhanced performance and advanced complexity of structures seen in the human form for audition and vision perception, for example, compared to other known structures that perform the same type of perception task with alternate sensory systems. Furthermore, AI agents created in the likeness of the human form currently appear to be very efficient at facilitating improved evolution and enactment of actions in a given environment [37].

As a result, the human form appears to be very efficient at dynamically adapting to the environment by virtue of its structure. This reasoning, stemming from the perspective founded in studies of cognition, leads us to the notion that although the pursuit of creating AI beings does not in itself favor one particular form, the current human form serves as a fine example of a blueprint with which to guide efforts at creating a first generation of more advanced AI beings which may or may not be exact matches to the human form.

Section 1.3: Principle #3

Principle #3:

Under no condition will the accountability of the AI being's actions rest with the AI being; a human party must always be identified as the party to be held accountable for the AI being's actions. Stated another way, the fault lies not with the creation but with the creator.

This principle addresses the consequences of AI beings' actions, particularly with regard to the parties meant to be held accountable for those actions. These parties may include, for example, the AI being's creators, or the AI being's owners. Research on accountability for actions of AI agents and robots [28] highlights that AI agents operating on large data sets towards making decisions, run the risk of behaving in ways that are harmful to society (e.g., through perpetuating biases). The research also highlights that one way to mitigate this risk is to task humans with scrutinizing the behaviors of the AI agents and to ensure that AI beings' decisions are *always under the jurisdiction of the human or party in a position to be accountable for the consequences of the AI beings' actions*, as alluded to in principle #1. The thinking that underlies the conception of our principle stems from ethical considerations of the use of AI technology [28]. Such a foundation in ethical considerations further enhances principle 1.2 in the OECD AI principles named "Respect for the rule of law, human rights and democratic values, including fairness and privacy" and principle 1.5, named "Accountability". Our principle enhances the said OECD's principles by explicitly recognizing that the AI actors creating the AI beings be aware of the accountability placed on them for actions carried out by the AI being. Moreover, it supports two foundational points: i) while being developed in our image, AI beings today and of the future are not live biological systems and do not process information by a mind/brain identical to ours and ii) that AI creators build AI systems with human well-being as a requisite outcome at their core.

Our principle indicates that AI beings are not to be treated in the same way as humans are treated regarding accountability. This idea is important for constraints on self-learning for AI agents, which is the subject of the following principle.

Section 1.4: Principle #4

Principle #4:

AI beings are to be designed with self-learning only to the extent that humans deem the self-learning acceptable for serving human values and interests.

Research from cognitive sciences, into building AI beings that can think in a manner that mimics human reasoning [38] has highlighted that a key part of human reasoning is the ability to learn-to-learn (i.e., the ability to self-learn new concepts or ideas). We view the ability to self-learn as crucial for building intelligent AI agents as indicated in recent research in computer science [39]. However, some measure of control ought to be imposed on the material learnt by an AI being; an AI being that thinks like a human can be useful but *only* up to the point at which the human finds that which the being learned does not align well with human interests. Specifically, *the AI being's self-learning cannot be uncontrolled*, it must be constrained and structured. The structure for self-learning may take its form from the purpose of the beings' creation; the beings'

self-learning can be constrained to only that which best serves human values and interests, including the consideration for reducing or eliminating biases and promoting inclusivity and fairness. One way to tackle the challenging task of defining how to establish a constrained set of self-learning outcomes is to decompose the task into two components:

- (a) Establish a capability for the AI beings to recognize they are learning something new. For example, design the being to self-check its knowledge base regularly and to identify if new knowledge has been gathered to a degree of confidence.
- (b) Establish a requirement for the AI being to automatically report what it has learned to a human party. This human party can have a role such as a self-learning overseer or a *self-learning governor*. This role would exist to check the acceptability of the newly learned self-learning outcome. We highlight that the role of the self-learning governor is proposed as a direct result of the introduction of AI beings in society. Particularly, this creates a very specific new type of job for humans because of the introduction of AI beings into society.

By combining the two above objectives, one can facilitate the creation of AI beings that can i) recognize the onset of new learning in their own database of knowledge and ii) present that learning to a human governor who can attest to the viability of that learning outcome as useful and thus in service of human interests.

Thus, by starting from a viewpoint founded in cognitive and computer sciences, our proposed principle expands on the OECD AI principle named "Inclusive growth, sustainable development and well-being". Specifically, the principle proposed in this section caters to advancing the inclusion of underrepresented populations, reducing economic, social, gender and other inequalities by controlling the self-learning ability of the AI beings to detect and eliminate any learnt harmful biases before they can be acted on by the AI beings.

One important aspect of integrating AI beings into human society is their interaction with each other and with humans. The following section addresses this issue.

Section 2: Interaction with AI

This theme concerns AI beings' place in society, the identity of AI beings, and the stance of human society towards AI beings, including issues such as emotion and empathy. This section is structured into three subsections, each targeting a specific sub-theme within the context of AI beings' interaction with humans and with each other, and the integration of humans with AI. The three subsections are:

Section 2.1.1: Humans reacting to AI in society

- The distinction: Establishing the ability of humans to distinguish AI agents from humans.
- The stop button: Enabling humans to stop any harmful activity as performed by AI.
- The protection of AI beings: Instilling laws to enable AI beings to perform their duties and protect AI beings against human aggression.

Section 2.1.2: AI's actions in society

- The creation of AI beings by other AI beings: Establishing a human stance towards AI beings creating other AI beings.
- The power of AI beings to recognize intelligence in other beings: Enabling AI beings to test other beings for intelligence under human supervision.

Section 2.1.3: Humans integrating with AI

- Human accountability at all times: The human is still accountable even if the human is integrated with AI.
- Controlled integration with AI: Integration while ensuring humans are still in control.

Section 2.1.1: Humans reacting to AI in society

2.1.1.1: The Distinction: Establishing the ability of humans to distinguish between AI beings and humans.

Principle #5

AI beings must be designed with a specific distinguishing factor or set of factors that allow humans to recognize the being they are addressing is not human. This requirement must be satisfied so that at least the creator of the AI being can demonstrate, beyond doubt, that it is, in fact, non-human. Put another way, under no condition is an AI being to be created without a clear, reliable method by which a human can prove its identity as an AI being.

This principle addresses the recognizability of AI beings in society and advocates for AI beings to be created with the directive to identify themselves when questioned about their identity. This principle expands upon current research focused on notifying users about AI output [40] towards empowering humans to directly enquire about the identity of the being they are addressing. Specifically, the principle goes beyond educating a human to recognize an AI beings' output and towards creating the AI being that is compelled to directly declare its identity upon being asked if it is an AI being. The line of reasoning originates from an engineering perspectives that argues for integrating the functionality of self-identification *within the construction of the AI being*. A complementary viewpoint from a perspective routed in cognition and computer sciences leads us to realize that our principle can also help alleviate some concerns about the well-known Turing test. The concern is that the Turing test merely establishes whether an AI agent can *behave in a way that is indistinguishable from that of a human* but does not explicitly address whether the agent actually *is or is not* a human. Along a similar vein, the idea that the Turing test may require some further refinements has been discussed [34], yet the focus of that discussion is about a being's reasoning, *given that it is an AI being*. We argue that the core reasoning mechanism of the AI being can potentially include *the declaration of the identity of the being*. In this way, this principle enables a human to instruct an AI being to identify itself unconditionally upon being questioned. Options to be taken towards an AI being that fails to respond to that questioning include its removal from society, its neutralization, or its elimination.

Therefore, this principle utilizes the reasoning from engineering and cognition and computer sciences to introduce a concept that is novel to OECD's AI principles, the

concept that the AI being is to be designed with the clear objective *to identify itself as an AI being upon being questioned*.

We do realize, however, that such a principle suffers from a potential shortcoming in the case whereby the purpose of the AI agent may be to integrate or even *infiltrate* a human group to the extent that its own programming *forbids such a self-identification* unless under extreme circumstances. We believe that such a situation constitutes an open question and is subject to potential future research.

2.1.1.2: The Stop Button: Enabling humans to immediately stop any harmful activity from AI.

Principle #6

AI beings must be designed with a cease-and-desist function, which acts as a 'stop action' command to safeguard against any actions that negatively impact human society.

This principle advocates for the establishment of safe actions or words to be used by humans to stop an AI being from committing any action that may harm a human being. This principle is designed to be used as a last resort for humans to stop any adverse actions from AI beings against humans, including acts that fall under Article 5 of the EU's AI Act [23]. We believe that in order to enable AI beings to continuously be able to respond when called upon to stop all activity, at least two requirements ought to be satisfied.

Firstly, the AI being must always be able to receive inputs from humans and to incorporate those inputs into its definition of its environment. This point is motivated and supported by research into the importance of the neural correlates within the context of awareness in humans [41], [42]. By incorporating that perspective from cognitive studies with the engineering perspective concerned with the design of AI being, we believe that the ability of an AI being to receive the inputs that propagate through its structure (one that may include neural correlates, for example), ought to form the foundation of its ability to sense its environment. As such, the main concept in this first point is that the being must constantly be able to receive human input, *including the command to stop*, through its sensing of its surrounding environment. The AI being must also consistently interpret that command in its intended purpose.

Secondly, the priority of the command to stop must be instilled in the AI agents' programming to the point where compliance with the stop command is seen as axiomatic; *under no condition is the agent meant to place a priority higher than that of a human who issues the AI agent with a 'stop' command*. From this viewpoint from engineering, we reason that a newly created AI being found not to comply with this principle, is an AI being that has failed the requirement to stop and is therefore deemed unfit to be released into human society. Further, if an AI being already deployed in society is found not to comply with the stop command, then options to take towards eliminating negative consequences from that being include its removal from society, its neutralization, or its elimination. We believe that one way to mitigate design or execution faults from AI beings not complying with the principle, is to consistently assess the AI being's ability to recognize and respond to the 'stop' command.

Therefore, our principle which originated from an engineering and cognitive science background, embeds context from principle 1.4 in OECD AI principles named “Robustness, security and Safety”, into the engineering and creation of an AI being. Further, our principle aligns with considerations of the purpose for which an AI being is deployed. That purpose may include functioning in domains that pose a significant risk to human wellbeing if AI beings are deployed. Such systems are referenced as high-risk AI systems as classified under the EU AI Act [23].

2.1.1.3: The protection of AI beings: Laws to enable AI beings to perform their duties.

Principle #7

Human aggression against AI beings is to be punishable by law, at least to the extent that the damage caused by human aggression is deemed to be damage to property owned by another human, or another human party accountable for the actions of the impacted AI being.

We realize that a currently pervasive issue in AI and machine learning is the potential for the technologies to reinforce biases that may (consciously or subconsciously) lead to unethical behaviors or decisions being made. One aspect we noted in research [43], [44], is that the research focused predominantly on biases that one group of humans may have against another, based on factors such as gender or race, for example. However, one bias that we envisage to appear in societies where humans and AI beings can co-exist is the bias a human can feel *towards an AI being*. We believe that this bias may not necessarily be driven by a view that AI beings are unjustly assuming roles once held by humans. This bias may stem from the view that the mere presence of AI beings is not welcomed by humans, regardless of the benefit they may bring to society. We reason that one possible outcome of this bias is acts of aggression against AI beings. However, we realize that biases or prejudices may not always drive such acts.

This principle recognizes that AI beings are to have an identity in human society. This identity includes either a recognition that the AI beings are represented in their own right as independent beings or are seen as tools (i.e. properties) worthy of protection under the law. It is our current view that this situation is best served by recognizing the view that the *minimum* penalty to be levied on a human aggressor against an AI being is the penalty established when treating AI beings as possessions (i.e., as tools as opposed to independent beings). In that way, the view that AI beings are tools may serve to set the minimum punishment to be levied on a human found to have caused damage to an AI being. Further punitive measures can be taken on a case-by-case basis as applicable.

As such, this principle starts from a viewpoint in ethics, and introduces a novel idea to OECD’s AI principles, the idea of establishing a *minimum level of punishment* for acts of human aggression against AI beings; a level that is established by viewing AI beings as properties worthy of protection under law. Such a principle protects the AI beings’ ability to function towards service of humans.

Principle #8

Human aggression against tools that are utilized by AI beings is to be legally punishable, as with principle 7. Further, such actions can potentially invalidate any contract that binds the AI being to perform its duties under any human ownership.

This principle recognizes that there may be cases when humans can, intentionally or unintentionally, cause damage to tools that an AI being may be using after seeking permission to obtain such tools to carry out its task. Such cases, though perhaps not highly probable that a human intentionally causes damage to tools utilized by an AI being, are nevertheless possible in practice and are to be treated with the same reasoning as in principle #7. With that reasoning, punitive measures levied on humans harming tools in use by AI beings are to be the same as those from principle #7. Further, the AI being can also be programmed to report (to the human party that created the AI being) cases where it cannot carry out its duties. As such, the AI being can indicate the consequences of harm that came to tools in its use as a result of human action.

This principle, like principle number 7, starts from an ethical viewpoint and introduces a concept that is novel to OECD's AI principles, the concept that the functionality of an AI being is negatively impacted not only by damage to *the form* of the AI being, but by damage to *any tools* that the AI being is using. This principle recognizes that acts of aggression against the tools used by AI beings, have a negative impact on the AI being's ability to function. As such, human aggression against tools used by AI beings, under our principle, ought to be an act that is legally punishable.

Section 2.1.2: AI's actions in society

2.1.2.1. The creation of AI beings by other AI beings

Principle #9

The creation of AI beings by other AI beings is allowed only to the extent that best serves humans.

This principle addresses one issue that is by far the most controversial: AI beings *creating other AI beings*. Specifically, this principle addresses a potential issue not yet seen in OECD principles, the eventuality that AI beings create other AI beings. One approach to perhaps mitigate the challenge posed by this principle is to bear in mind the purpose of creating AI beings: to best serve humans. This principle underlies the authors' choice to hold the view that AI beings creating other AI beings is not an immediately objectionable eventuality, particularly if we believe that the created being may have the potential to serve humanity. Once one considers the importance of serving human interests, two scenarios emerge in which we envisage AI beings creating other AI beings.

One scenario includes the case in which a company or human party intentionally uses AI beings for the purpose of creating other beings in a controlled environment akin to the use of the genetic algorithm seen in AI engineering studies [45]. Such an approach is not only *not objectionable* but is also, in our view, highly conducive to improving the evolution of AI beings towards better performance in their environments. By using top performing AI beings to create other AI beings, we may realize a potential approach

to a faster evolution of AI beings' forms. Indeed, research that addresses evolution [35], [37] highlights its importance when determining the best form of a being intended to exist in an environment. With this line of thinking, adopting this principle enables AI beings to create other AI beings in a controlled environment, bearing the potential to more efficiently realize improved, more highly evolved AI beings to better serve humans.

The second scenario is by far the most controversial whereby AI beings *spontaneously* create other AI beings without the input from humans. In this scenario, we again encourage considering the importance of serving humans. We believe that the probability of this scenario materializing cannot be definitively stated to be zero, and we reason that it is prudent to instill regulations and laws to address such an event if it occurs. We believe that this principle enables effective governance of AI beings, a governance that is robust against rationales questioning whether the act of AI beings creating other AI beings requires consciousness. The principle effectively eliminates this concern about the requirement of consciousness if AI beings create other AI beings. Given the insufficiency of tests of awareness for humans as witnessed in current research [46], our principle addresses this question of requiring awareness for AI beings. Specifically, we reason that being prepared for the event of AI beings creating other AI being brings benefits in two scenarios: a) a scenario in which the level of consciousness needed to carryout the creation is *known*, and b) a scenario in which the level of consciousness needed for creation is *unknown*.

Furthermore, one of the most important considerations in this scenario is that the created AI being is to be treated and tested in the same way as newly created AI beings by humans (i.e., to be tested in terms of its suitability for serving human values and interests, failure to pass those tests leads to the AI being being removed, neutralized or eliminated). However, we realize that the most difficult question in this scenario is establishing a human party to be accountable for the actions of the AI-created being, as stated in principle number 3. It is our current view that the human who foresees value in the AI being and can prove that it can comply with the aforementioned principles of creation is the party first nominated for that accountability. Yet, we realize that practical limitations associated with holding humans accountable for actions of a creation *not made by humans* may lead to the AI-created beings having a very limited scope of existence if allowed to exist at all.

Nevertheless, it is our view that *controlled* AI-to-AI creation can be a very useful step towards realizing the merits of genetic mutation algorithms on a much larger scale; AI beings can be selected to pair with other AI beings towards favored AI characteristics, thereby not eliminating the possibility of allowing AI beings to create other AI beings. Yet, such creation ought to be done under human supervision and accountability.

As such, our principle starts from perspectives including AI engineering and ethics and introduces a new concept to OECD's AI principles, the concept of AI beings creating other AI beings. Our principle also specifies actions to be taken in response to such an event.

2.1.2.2. The power of AI beings to recognize other beings

Principle #10:

AI beings are bound to play a role that includes the assessment of the intelligence of other beings. Humans must adhere to standards to test the AI beings that test the other beings for signs of human behavior and human-like intelligence.

Although this section does not advocate for a principle per se, it attempts to answer this question: “Would we choose to enable or allow the breadth of intelligence of AI beings to include the *intelligence assessment* of other beings? Are we comfortable with an assessment of intelligence by a being *which itself is not human*?”

We believe that the answer to this question may come not in the form of a choice but as an inevitable practical constraint that may arise because of the widespread existence of AI beings amongst humans. We reason that the being determining whether another being demonstrates intelligence comparable to that of a human *may itself not be human*. We believe that this situation may arise not because AI beings are believed to be better suited than humans for that job, but because that job may require far more humans than at first imagined to be necessary. Furthermore, research into the efficacy of tests devised to judge intelligence, such as the Turing test [34], or tools to test awareness, such as the perturbational complexity index [42], hint that methods of the Turing test alone are not sufficient to comprehensively judge the level of intelligence of an AI being; the Turing test may not be sufficient to judge whether an agent possesses enough intelligence to pass as a human. By that reasoning, such tests may benefit from a well-supervised AI being that conducts the test on behalf of humans and uses far more advanced technology to test intelligence, more than a human could reasonably test.

By that reasoning, the principle advocated for in this section started from a practical viewpoint regarding the challenge of catering for a large number of tests to determine intelligence, to arrive at a view that is akin to an axiomatic law that we believe will likely be observed in the future. We also reason, however, that adopting this principle potentially leads to a new role for humans: the role of *the supervisor of the AI beings testing other AI beings*.

Section 2.1.3: Humans integrating with AI

2.1.3.1. Controlled integration with AI

Principle #11:

In the event that a human is integrated with an AI being of any shape or form, the accountability for all actions taken by the hybrid being rests with the human part of the hybrid being. The only exceptions are cases when the AI beings’ manufacturing party acknowledges, through a regular inspection, that the AI component of the hybrid being is at fault, in which case the manufacturing entity is responsible for correcting flaws.

This principle applies if and when AI technology reaches a point at which humans can integrate with AI beings, on a level that is not only merely physical, such as with prosthetics, but at a level that is perhaps molecular or biological. This integration can

be at a level that goes *beyond* using a brain-controlled interface (BCI), as alluded to in research [44], [47] considering current proposals on neural ethics and neural rights [48], and towards systems that include AI beings that act on behalf of the human. If and when that level of integration happens, it can lead to the presence of *hybrid* beings; beings that are part *human* and part *AI being*. The principle we propose argues that the accountability for the actions taken by the hybrid being *ought to rest with the human part of the hybrid being*, particularly the human who is integrated with, and controlling, the hybrid being. The principle addresses a potential concern about the proliferation of the practice of integrating humans with AI technology: *the loss of autonomy of the humans*. Indeed, research on this topic [49] has highlighted the need for principled ethical governance structures regarding the continued autonomy of the human who integrated with AI technology, thereby highlighting that the proposed principle is one step towards establishing ethical governance towards facilitating the sustainable creation and operation of hybrid beings. Furthermore, we reason that the principle is aligned with the rationale of our proposed principle number 3 in terms of human accountability, and also potentially mitigates highly complex investigations into the distinction of accountability between the human part and the AI being part of the hybrid, in terms of the origin of a decision made or action taken by the hybrid being.

One assumption that we make in establishing this principle, an assumption which may be somewhat controversial, is that the human *chooses* to integrate with the AI being. The context in which such a choice made can be a quite a difficult one to comprehensively define, and in some cases the choice may not always be an easy one to make, if it was a choice at all particularly if the integration was a medical necessity or a government-mandated action for example. What is fundamental in our view is that any negative consequences stemming from a poor judgement, decision or action due to a hybrid being that is unduly influenced by its AI component, *rests with the human who chose to integrate with the AI being*. One way to mitigate the negative consequences of integration is to instigate regular maintenance checkups (on the AI part of the hybrid being) by the producing or manufacturing company. Such checkups can confirm the absence of faults relating to the AI parts' functioning or faults related to poor security against hacking the AI part of the hybrid being. We do acknowledge, though, that checkups do not necessarily eliminate the probability of a potentially harmful action from a hybrid being without clear accountability being levied on the human. However, such checkups can at least minimize the negative consequences of such an event by attempting to mitigate AI-component faults as early as possible.

The application of a law that finds the human-AI being accountable may come under some pressure if human-AI integration is widely adopted; a detected AI fault may affect a large number of hybrid human-AI beings, rendering an individual case-by-case investigation unviable. We believe that mitigating such an eventuality remains an open question under this principle.

Worthy of note is the possibility of integrating *data from an AI being into a human* during the integration; such an act can be akin to downloading data directly into the human mind in the form of a data bank that the human can access. Though not necessarily a problem in and of itself, this action runs the risk of potentially influencing the actions of the human to the point at which a human may not be effectively controlling the hybrid-being; the human may become so reliant on the information that the AI being supplies, that the AI being essentially *controls the human by potentially*

misleading the human through supplying biased or otherwise faulty information. Such a discussion raises the question of free will in the hybrid agent (e.g., who has the free will? Is it the human part that takes action? Or is it the AI being that provides the human with the information after integration?). We believe that such a question is likely to remain open for current and subsequent research [48]. However, we do maintain that the principle highlights the necessary accountability to the human who integrates with the AI being, for actions by the hybrid being.

Therefore, this principle starts from an ethical viewpoint and introduces a novel idea to OECD's AI principles, the idea of assimilation or integration of humans with AI beings, and specifically the establishment of accountability to the human part of the hybrid being for the actions of that hybrid being.

Principle #12:

Human integration with AI beings is to be allowed only to the point beyond which a human is not deemed in full control of, or in charge of, commanding the hybrid being.

This principle addresses a key assumption made in principle 11; the assumption that the human part of the hybrid being is in control of the hybrid being.

If and when human-AI integration occurs as described in principle 11, one question that could arise is whether the human part of these hybrid beings is still in charge of commanding the hybrid being. Such a question may be answered by attempting to determine the point at which the human part of the hybrid being is no longer in control of the hybrid being. This point at which the human is no longer in charge of commanding the hybrid human-AI agent is quite difficult to establish, and we believe it is very likely to be and will remain an open research question. If that point has been reached, however, we believe that the hybrid being is to at least be removed from society (either imprisoned or quarantined) and, at worst, eliminated for failing to serve humans.

In our view, a key consideration with hybrid beings is the accountability for faults in the *design or operation* of the AI components of the hybrid beings, or faults in the *interface between the human and the AI components* of the hybrid being. The difficulty of establishing accountability for harm to society stemming from faulty AI components in a hybrid-being is likely to be a major obstacle to establishing a deterrent to poorly produced AI components that get integrated with humans. In a situation where a hybrid-being commits an offense or a fault and the fault was discovered to be caused by a faulty AI component, it is quite predictable that the companies or parties manufacturing the AI components will attempt to prove that the human was still in control. However, we note that in the event of a repeated fault from a poorly manufactured AI component, public opinion is very likely to negatively impact the creating or manufacturing party despite the party not being found legally guilty of any wrongdoing. In other words, simply because the AI-creating company could not *legally be proven guilty*, public opinion could negatively impact that company's reputation to the extent that the company cannot continue to create or operate faulty equipment in the future.

Furthermore, it is also possible that faults could emerge not from the AI components but from their *interface with the human counterpart in the hybrid agent*. In this case, one approach to mitigate faults at this interface between the human and the AI being

may be to place benchmarks on the quality of this interface before adoption (i.e., establish a benchmark for the quality of the interface before the integration occurs) and ensure that consequences of failing to meet the benchmarking requirement include stoppage of the manufacturing of the AI being from the creating company, or revoking that company's license to operate.

As such, this principle, like principle number 11, starts from an ethical perspective, and introduces the idea of governing the extent of assimilation of humans with AI beings. An idea that is novel to OECD's AI principles. Such a principle is vital for effective governance of hybrid beings.

Conclusion

This paper outlined principles to govern the creation of AI beings. The Twelve principles in this paper addressed issues related to two themes: the purpose of creating AI beings and the interaction of AI beings. We believe that the principles we propose can enhance the OECD AI principles by widening their scope of application and introducing ideas, novel to OECD's AI principles, to facilitate governing the creation and operation of AGI. Moreover, our principles also expand upon the current OECD principles' focus on AI heading *towards AGI*, thereby broadening the impact of principle adoption. We also reason that targeting of foreseeable issues of AI technology with these principles complements current regulatory frameworks, which focus on current and near future frontier AI model issues facing AI technology. Further, our principles lead to potential new roles or jobs for humans that would unlock new opportunities for human employment; opportunities that are potentially within the grasp of motivated and conscientious human contributors. For these reasons, it is our view that the principles we propose in this paper are to be adopted and ratified through international cooperation across salient institutions that target governance and creation of AI systems.

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